



Figure S3a. Climate in Eocene in the region of Baltic amber formation (orange arrow) and in southernmost region of South America (green arrow) was similar, described as warm (85 Scotese 2012). Orange arrow: Baltic amber presumed locality of *Maietta* (*Hoffeinsoneura*) *christelae*, n. sp.; green arrow: recent locality of extant species of *Maietta*.



Figure S3b. Geographical distribution of *Maietta* in South America: a) Nahuelbuta forest; b) Chiloé evergreen forest; c) Aysén.

Nahuelbuta: Specimens are collected near water bodies or islands, some of them at significant altitudes (over 1km), where winters are frequently snowy. According to [76](#) Smith-Ramirez (2004), “The Nahuelbuta forest: Meteorological data are lacking for higher elevations, but precipitation is probably greater than that recorded at sea level, with frequent winter snowfall above 1000 m. The minimum mensal average temperature recorded in Concepcion was 8.7°C (July 1998 and 1999), and the maximum mensal average temperature was 16.6°C ([95](#) Conama 1999)”.

Isla Chiloe evergreen rain forest. The Chilean coastal range: a vanishing center of biodiversity and endemism in South American temperate rainforests. There is no snow commonly in these places. Chiloe evergreen forests: an annual precipitation between 5000 and 6000 mm ([96](#) Perez et al. 1998). Mean monthly temperatures at sea level vary between 6°C in July and a maximum of 16°C in January”.

Aysen, the southernmost and coldest locality: average temperature for coldest month, July, from -3 to +3°C; for warmest, January, 7-17°C; (source: <https://en.climate-data.org/south-america/chile/region-aysen-del-general-carlos-ibanez-del-campo/valle-simpson-876092/#temperature-graph>). This climate seems similar to southern Scandinavia; for example, Karlskrona, southern Sweden: Jan. -1.5 to +3 °C, July 15-17 °C (source: <https://en.climate-data.org/europe/sweden/blekinge-laen/karlskrona-6274/#temperature-graph>, respectively).